

STOMACH ULCER AND METHODS OF ITS TREATMENT.

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10622798>

Abstract

The stomach contains acid that aids in digestion. But it can also digest the walls of the organ. To prevent this, the inner mucous part of the stomach is covered with a layer of protective cells that it actively produces. If for some reason this layer is destroyed, the mucus decreases, the acid starts to eat the stomach wall. In this way, a wound is formed.

Key words: *peptic ulcer, Helicobacter pylori, gastritis, Zollinger-Ellison syndrome.*

A peptic ulcer is an open wound in the lining of the stomach. Sometimes similar ulcers appear in the part of the intestine located behind the stomach. In this case, it is a duodenal ulcer. Both types of stomach ulcers are called peptic ulcers. They appear, develop and are treated according to the same scenario. Therefore, the concept of peptic ulcer can be said to be an exact synonym of gastric ulcer.

Peptic ulcers are very common. For example, in the United States, one in ten people suffer from this disease.

The older the age, the higher the risk of developing stomach ulcers. This disease is especially common in people over 60 years old.

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There are several factors that can break the protective layer.

1. Bacterial infection.

Often, bacteria called *Helicobacter pylori* (*H. pylori*) that enter the stomach from unwashed hands or other objects damage the protective layer. In some conditions, these microbes first cause inflammation of the gastric mucosa (gastritis), and then destroy the integrity of the protective layer.

Surprisingly, up to 50% of the world's population is infected with *Helicobacter pylori* bacteria. But in most cases it does not seriously affect health. Gastric ulcers develop in only 10-15% of those infected.

2. Taking some painkillers.

Nonsteroidal anti-inflammatory drugs (NSAIDs) are known to cause ulcers, such as:

Aspirin. Although the tablets are covered with a protective shell and dissolve outside the stomach.

- Means based on ibuprofen.
- Preparations based on diclofenac sodium.
- Pain relievers based on naproxen.
- Some prescription NSAIDs.

Means based on paracetamol do not belong to non-steroidal anti-inflammatory drugs and they do not harm the protective layer of the stomach.

It's important to note that not everyone who takes NSAIDs develops ulcers. The risk increases if painkillers enter a stomach already infected with *Helicobacter pylori* bacteria. Also, taking non-steroidal anti-inflammatory drugs can be doubly dangerous if:

- If painkillers are drunk uncontrollably, without following the instructions, if they increase the dose.
- If NSAIDs are taken for several days in a row.
- When over 70 years old.
- When taking corticosteroids. Such drugs are prescribed for asthma, arthritis.
- Once a peptic ulcer is diagnosed.
- 3. Some lifestyle factors

In the past, there was a view that spicy foods, coffee, alcohol and stress thin the protective layer of the stomach. But there is not enough evidence for this.

A more proven harmful factor — smoking can cause the formation of stomach ulcers and reduce the effectiveness of treatment.

4. Other reasons.

In rare cases, stomach ulcers can appear against the background of the following diseases and conditions:

- Severe infectious diseases;
- Abdominal surgery;
- Taking certain medications, such as steroids;

A rare disease called Zollinger-Ellison syndrome in which a tumor (gastrinoma) occurs in the acid-producing cells.

Sometimes nothing. If the stomach ulcer is small, the body will overcome it by itself. The wound on the stomach lining will heal and the digestive system will resume normal functioning.

But it doesn't always end that way. In some cases, the wound expands and deepens. If not treated in time, it can reach the blood vessels. This condition causes internal bleeding along with a lot of blood loss.

Another unpleasant complication occurs when the wound deepens. Through the resulting opening, stomach or intestinal contents pass into the abdominal cavity, which leads to peritonitis. Inflammation of the abdominal cavity, if not stopped in time, can lead to blood poisoning, failure of vital organs and even sudden death.

It is impossible to predict how events will develop in the case of a patient without a medical examination. Therefore, it is very important to know the symptoms of stomach ulcers, if they appear, it is necessary to consult a doctor as soon as possible.

What are the symptoms of a stomach ulcer and when should you see a doctor?

- Sometimes there are no symptoms. But most of the time, stomach ulcers appear as characteristic symptoms.
- There is a burning, cutting pain in the upper central part of the abdomen. This is especially evident on an empty stomach.
- The pain decreases after eating or taking medication.
- Nausea or vomiting occurs regularly.
- A boil is observed.

If at least two of these symptoms are felt, it is necessary to consult a general practitioner or a gastroenterologist as soon as possible.

Even if there are symptoms of stomach ulcer complications, it is necessary to call an ambulance. Vomiting that is bloody or dark brown in color. Sudden increase in sharp pain in the abdomen.

How to treat a stomach ulcer?

Treatment depends on the exact cause of the ulcer. If the doctor's instructions are strictly followed, it is possible to get rid of a stomach ulcer within one or two months.

The following may be prescribed for treatment:

- Antibiotics. Such drugs are prescribed if the protective layer of the stomach is damaged by a bacterial infection.
- Medicines that reduce the production of acid in the stomach.

- Antacids, their function is to reduce the acidity of the stomach, that is, to neutralize gastric juice.
- Protective equipment. When taken, they cover the wound with a protective layer, that is, they serve as a kind of liquid bandage.
- If the wound bleeds, surgery will be necessary. Doctors insert a special probe into the stomach and use it to clamp or cauterize the edges of the wound to stop bleeding.

What to do to prevent peptic ulcer?

There is no guarantee that the wound will not appear clearly. But there are several ways to reduce the risks:

- Avoid taking non-steroidal anti-inflammatory drugs (NSAIDs) unless necessary.
- If fever or pain relief is needed, choose the lowest effective dose of NSAIDs. All this will be written in the instructions.
- Take NSAIDs with food.
- Discuss with your therapist which pain reliever is the safest for you. You can find an alternative to non-steroidal anti-inflammatory drugs.

In addition, if the disease has been diagnosed, there are secondary prevention measures. They are aimed at preventing recurrence of the disease and preventing its complications. For this, it is important to regularly meet with the attending physician and follow his recommendations. In case of exacerbation of the disease, it is necessary to take therapeutic courses, especially in spring and autumn.

It is important that the patient follows a diet and does not eat forbidden foods. Long walks in the open air, treatment in sanatoriums are also useful. According to the doctor's recommendation, a continuous course of antisecretory drugs can be prescribed.

If there are no exacerbations of stomach ulcers for three years or more, it is possible to talk about complete remission of the disease.

As for the prognosis of recovery, it is positive if the disease is detected in time. Adequate therapy and, if necessary, the patient's consent to surgical intervention are also important. The prognosis is negative when the disease causes complications.

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